

PRE-SCHOOL PREPARATION MODERN APPROACHES TO THE FORMATION OF SPEECH COMPRESSIONS OF YOUNG CHILDREN

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Annotation: *The article highlights modern approaches to the formation of speech compressions of children of preschool age, their application in practical life and the importance of their effectiveness.*

Keywords: *speech, knowledge, skills, qualification, NURI training program, competence, integral activity, didactic play, communication, oral speech, social attitude.*

President of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev, who is leading our country without deviation from the path of independent development, let's not take what sphere, we can not achieve any changes, a comfortable life without training modern mature personnel. The training of such personnel, the healthy gene pool of the nation, begins, first of all, from the pre-school education system."not only the representatives of the sphere, but also each of us has become our motto. In fact, if the root of any tree with its salutary is deep and firmly entrenched, then this tree will turn into the most solid and magnificent tree and will blossom. Consequently, the educational system is also considered to be the root of the same tree as preschool education, if we take on the example of a tree. Therefore, we must first of all start with the pre-school age to raise the level of education and training of highly qualified personnel. In this regard, our president also pays special attention to the preschool training system. After all, during the visit of the president of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Republic of South Korea on November 22-24, 2017, about 20 meetings were held by the Ministry of pre-school education and exchange of experience. In Uzbekistan, agreements were reached on the opening of kindergartens in an experimental way, training of Joint Personnel and studying opportunities for conducting scientific research. Within the framework of the visit, they gave information about the stages of preschool education and child care, the principles of developing strategies for the development of the industry, the implementation of the „national program NURI preschool education". Currently, the national program of preschool education "NURI" is being used in practice. the essence of this program :

- harmonious development of body and soul health;
- formation of the basis of democratic citizens ;
- connecting the primary school curriculum in the care process of children from the first age to the age of two ;

- formation of a healthy lifestyle;
- emphasize the shape of the child's personality;
- physical development and activity;
- to develop respect for the culture of other nations;
- to provide a safe environment for the child

The methods used in teaching and learning process are as follows:

- teaching and development through the game;
- to give leave with emphasis on the child's upbringing and thus ensure the continuity of education;
- to help to form knowledge,skill qualifications and values based on the experience of the child;
- provide activities between child and teacher, child and child, child and the surrounding world;
- to provide subject-based integrated activities;
- Internal-external activities, static-dynamic activities activities of large small groups and individual activities ,recreation and balanced activities amaga increase;
- the interest of children is to carry out the learning process in a way that is appropriate for each child, taking into account development and environmental relations.

Objectives of the beam process;

- a healthy person
- independent person
- creative person
- a person full of emotions
- a person who lives in a society

At present, the majority is considered the base program of kindergarten,the first step “like the state program NURI program is reflected in the areas of development of the child.We will.

1.Physical education,
health
- enjoy physical
activity;
-to be healthy;
- safe hyot
forgiveness;

2.Communication -
speech and
communication;
-organising reading
and writing;
-enjoy books and
stories.

3.Social relations
-self-awareness and
respect;
-to live with others;
- interest in society

The program we reviewed above is the educational system of South Korea, which is close to us with its values, customs and traditions, and according to statistics, the educational system in this state is highly developed. In our country, too, the South Korea model is currently being used in the field of pre-school education in order to raise the educational system to high figures.

The link that connects continuing education (kindergarten and school) is the preparatory groups for this school. Therefore, it is worthwhile to organize training in training groups more effectively than in other groups. Consequently, by this age (6-7), the development of mathematics and lexicon in their speech will continue, speech will become fluent. Word wealth increases, children begin to use generalizing nouns, begin to use synonyms, antonyms and adjectives. If there is a lot of reading and communication with the child, then by this age, both monological speech (explanatory and interpretive, descriptive speech) and skills for participation in communication are well formed. Written speech begins to form. Word wealth is rich up to about 3 000 thousand words. During training, the use of a lot of techniques, didactic games also gives a good effect.

In speech-growing classes in preparatory groups, as an example, if I have a magic wand! ", „ Do not say the name ” can apply didactic games like.

„ If magic wand! “ didactic game .

In this game, children get settled in the form of a circle. In the middle put a magic wand (it can be an item). The educator tells the children to take one stick at a time. One of the children takes a stick and starts his story: „ if I have a magic wand I would like to have a big toy then my dad would like me to bring a lot of ice cream! “ this is how each child builds a small story that consists of his worldview and desires.

“Do not say the name “ didactic game.

In this game, the educator calls one of the children next to him and says a word (the name of something or event). And the child is forbidden to throw this word himself. The child in front of the educator should give a different interpretation, which will suit him, and not the name he is told and his characteristics. For example, the flower”. The child standing in front of the educator gives such comments „ there at the beginning of Sabina expresses through such words as’ or, „ abdulaziz broke it’. Children need to find his name.

Children are in the process of these games :

he hears and understands speech;

in his speech, he uses correct pronunciation, convenient grammatical forms and various sentence constructions;

second language shows interest in learning;

second language shows his initial knowledge on possession;

shows interest in works of art literature; will have an idea of the lexical, syllable and phonetic structure of the word;

knows how to independently compose and pronounce different forms of meaning;

The above-mentioned techniques, the main function of didactic games, consists in the formation of children's speech compensations.

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